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Solidarity and Fraternity of All Brothers and Sisters: A Creative Reading of *Fratelli tutti*

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Abstract: The Encyclical *Fratelli Tutti*, is an urgent appeal to all the citizens and faith-believers of the world to course-direct on a different path, for the survival of the world. The author makes a re-reading of the document, calling for social action through a creative social friendship and fraternity while underlining the key points in the document. This paper highlights on the theme of socio-political love. Positively, the author agrees that as a *Social Encyclical*, it would do well towards social friendship and support a culture of encounter. In this process, inter-faith dialogue, solidarity and forgiveness could contribute much towards an ecumenical and global renewal. With an inclusive approach to life and faith, the author affirms the inter-faith fraternity for the common good. In this context, the religious leaders will have to be authentic mediators in the name of human fraternity, by being at the service of all brothers and sisters.

Keywords: Fraternity, Solidarity, Social Friendship, , Fratelli tutti, Inter-Faith Dialogue

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Pope Francis has signed his “Social Encyclical” *Fratelli tutti* (FT 6; Francis, 2020)¹ on 3rd October, 2020 in Assisi, with an urgent call to all men and women on earth to follow the example of Jesus. By addressing persons by the loveable words ‘brothers’ and ‘sisters’, people of all caste, colour and creed, we wish to find a close bond with others beyond the blood relation. In daily social living, strangers and neighbours are made into ‘brothers’ and ‘sisters’. Christians too, win the hearts of people by addressing them with the same familiar words with love. They are expressions of family experience with close ties - words that all cultures and all times comprehend. They are evocative signs of solidarity which is inscribed at the heart of our common humanity. From the Biblical times and even earlier, history proved that to be close to others is to “experience the violence of Cain, the greed of Jacob, the jealousy of Joseph’s brothers” (Henning, 2020) and yet human beings continued to love the ‘other’ who is not one of its kin.

The encyclical FT is Francis’ vision for a post-pandemic world. It brings together themes that Pope Francis has underscored in various contexts over the past years of his pontificate. This first-of-a-kind document embraces ‘brotherhood’ among different religions, and calls for religious freedom, condemning religious persecution. The Covid-19 pandemic proves that “no one can face life in isolation”. Therefore, certain ideals with some tangible ways are laid out in FT for unitedly building a more just and fraternal world in daily relationships, in social life, politics and institutions, etc. The time has truly come to “dream, then, as a single human family” of “brothers and sisters all” (FT 7-8).

¹ Pope Francis’ 200-page third Encyclical Letter “Fratelli tutti” (henceforth FT) on *Fraternity and Social Friendship*, was published on 4th October 2020, on the occasion of the feast of Saint Francis of Assisi. This was inspired by St. Francis, like the Pontiff’s second Encyclical *Laudato Si*, on the Care of Our Common Home, marking the first Encyclical on ecology.

Keeping the purpose of Francis' writing of the Encyclical, i.e. solidarity, fraternity and social friendship among all brothers and sisters on earth, the author delves into a different reading of *Fratelli tutti*, while underlining the key points in the document, which is addressed to the entire Church, as well as to the whole world. With a particular key to understanding Pope Francis' appeal to the world, the author elaborates on the real family bond of fraternity and the local community. Taking the clue from Francis, this paper visions out an open heart, and how that has to be done in order to open itself to others in the world with love and concern, through social friendship, respecting the dignity of each person as brother and sister. This can enhance a universal fraternity, holding to human rights, and by fulfilling the societal responsibilities by all the stakeholders in the world. This needs to be done following the model of the Good Samaritan, through a better kind of politics that is at the service of the common good. In this context, the Church as a whole has to fulfill its socio-political task following the paths of renewed encounter and forgiveness, and not just remain naïve.

Following the courageous yet fragile, bold but non-violent universal leaders: Francis of Assisi, Martin Luther King, Desmond Tutu, Mahatma Gandhi, Blessed Charles de Foucauld and Pope Francis himself, the present author confirms that the present world religious leaders will have to be "authentic mediators" in the name of human fraternity, through dialogue, common cooperation, mutual knowledge and respect. The world religious leaders will have to be at the service of enhancing universal brotherhood and unity, beyond all caste, creed and affiliations, thus establishing peace and justice through genuine inter-faith fraternal dialogue. The author invites all to co-create together a world that is built on love, forgiveness, justice, equality, and together inspire change of policies, practices, and behaviour at all levels.

Keys to Understanding *Fratelli Tutti*: Fraternity and Social Friendship

The third encyclical of Pope Francis, after *Lumen fidei* (2013) and *Laudato Si'* (2015), *Fratelli tutti of fraternity and social friendship*, consists in treading on the dark clouds over a closed world, meeting the need of the strangers on the road - poor, migrants, neighbours in most need - envisaging and engendering an open world with a heart open to the whole creation by means of better kind of politics, dialogue and friendship in the society, through the willing and self-sacrificing paths of renewed encounter. A relatively long magisterial document, the encyclical FT that calls for fraternity and social friendship, is a summary of Pope Francis's thoughts garnered over the past years as people's priest and a pope of the periphery. According to Pope Francis, St. Francis of Assisi "did not wage a war of words aimed at imposing doctrines; he simply spread the love of God (...) and inspired the vision of a fraternal society" (FT 2-4). We have common membership in the human family, for we are the children of one Creator; and that in a globalized and interconnected post-pandemic world, only together can we be saved.

The Grand Imam of Al-Azhar says, "*Fratelli tutti*, is an extension of the Document on Human Fraternity, and reveals a global reality in which the vulnerable and marginalized pay the price for unstable positions and decisions (...) It is a message that is directed to people of good will, whose consciences are alive and restores to humanity consciousness."² In fact, FT is based on fraternity and social friendship that have concerned the Pope in recent years and on the

² Grand Imam Ahmad Al-Tayyeb, reacts in his Tweet, to the release of Pope Francis's Encyclical, *Fratelli tutti*, stating that Pope Francis "restores to humanity its consciousness." Al-Tayyeb co-signed the Document on *Human Fraternity for World Peace and Living Together* with Pope Francis in February 2019 in Abu Dhabi. FT contains several citations from the Document on Human Fraternity.

themes put forward in the *Document on Human Fraternity for World Peace and Living Together*, in February 2019.

The document opens with a rather “bleak assessment of the current state of the world”(Le Normand, 2020) stating that all brothers and sisters without borders are going through the “dark clouds over a closed world” (Ch. 1, FT 9-55) and “shattered dreams”, that seem to be the end of historical and human consciousness, lacking a proactive plan for everyone (FT15-28). Shadows over the closed world spread everywhere, “plunge humanity into confusion, loneliness, and desolation”. FT alarms against a “culture of walls”, of organized crime, fueled by fear (FT 27-28). With a “throwaway” culture in the world today, with insufficient universal human rights often being violated; within certain conflict and fear in the midst of globalization and progress, yet without a shared and decisive roadmap (FT 29-31). As the present pandemics and other calamities in history have proven, there has been an absence of human dignity on the peripheral borders (FT 37-41), with mixed feelings on the illusion of communication, shameless aggressions on various areas, and having information without wisdom (FT 42). The mass media has deteriorated ethics (FT 29), creating isolated virtual circles without freedom and constructive dialogue (FT 43-50).

Francis observes trends in our world that hinder the development of universal fraternity. According to him, “Globalized society makes us neighbours, but it does not make us brothers” (*intended sisters too!*, FT 12; Francis, 2014:1; *Caritas in Veritate*, CV19). The grey and dark clouds over a world that is so closed up on itself are observed in: the despair and discouragement that are widespread in society; the polarization that impedes dialogue and living together; the persons who are considered easily “sacrificed” and discarded; the inequality of rights and the new forms of slavery; and the moral deterioration and the weakening of spiritual values. Today one witnesses the manipulation and deformation of concepts such as, liberty, unity, democracy, freedom and justice; social community

and history; selfishness and indifference toward the common good; market logic based on profit and the culture of waste; unemployment, racism, poverty; disparity of rights; slavery, women and organ trafficking, subjugation of women, etc. (FT 10-24). In the face of these challenges, FT insists that “The road we must travel is that of closeness; it is the culture of encounter” with hope (FT 30); that God continues to sow abundant seeds of goodness, together with love, justice and solidarity, that has to be realized each day. It is with hope that we look beyond any personal convenience that limits our horizon, and it opens us up to grand ideals.

He warns that there are existing “signs of a certain regression” (FT 11). For him, words like democracy, freedom, justice or unity “have been bent and shaped to serve as tools for domination”, and “to justify any action” (FT 14) by the powerful. Therefore, the first victims of such self-centred agenda and xenophobia, are the voiceless poor. The document is a cry of alarm against demagogic populism. A false and “closed populist groups distort the word ‘people’” (FT 160), and this “unhealthy” and “irresponsible” populism by some political leaders who “seek popularity by appealing to the basest and most selfish inclinations of certain sectors of the population,” (FT 159) has to be denounced. Global problems call for global actions. The resurgence of nationalism, calls for a reformed, more ‘family-like’ United Nations. Pope Francis, a follower of “the theology of the people” says, “each of us is fully a person when we are part of a people” (FT 182). Therefore, he does not disqualify “people”.³ Living within multiple forms of subjection and of self-contempt (FT 51, 53), there is still a ray of hope always.

The document proposes that it is a social encyclical dedicated to putting forth a new vision of fraternity and social friendship, while treating the universal dimension of the doctrine of fraternal love.

³ The word ‘*people*’ appears 95 times in the new encyclical, FT.

The title *Fratelli tutti* being an expression of Saint Francis of Assisi (Admonitions, 6.1)⁴, is an evocative that encourages all to dream as a single human family and as fellow travellers sharing the same flesh. It is invitation to all men and women who will accept this reflection, and enter into a dialogue with love, that transcends the barriers of geography and distance. Pope Francis concludes the document with this prayerful wish: “Come, Holy Spirit, show us your beauty, reflected in all the peoples of the earth, so that we may discover anew that all are important and all are necessary, different faces of the one humanity that God so loves.”

Family Bond of Fraternity and Community

Family is part of one’s life and living. It cannot be chosen. One is born into it. A larger family called a community becomes a deliberately chosen social structure, which can be a source of rivalry, of jealousy. Then it becomes a problem to live in. Just as one shares the same space in the family, one learns to manage conflicts in family and community. Brothers and sisters of blood prefer to exist for what they are, having their identity, role and respect in their family. The first social nucleus is a gift from God that we receive, preserve and invest into. Yet, it has to be nourished by a certain form of friendship and closeness in order to commit to it as members. Often enough, the family or group of families can turn into a clan. We all are part of one community or the other, either chosen by will or born into. And here, we hear often the possessive pronouns - “my brother”, “my sister”. So often the priests address the congregation with these ‘dearness’; terms, expressing a common space, and a shared identity. This is true of the family, as well as of an “elective community, which creates a boundary, defines a belonging.”

⁴ Saint Francis of Assisi used the expression *Fratelli Tutti*, to propose a way of life marked by the flavour of the Gospel.

Jean-Jacques Goldman, a popular French singer wrote: “You are part of my community, the one I have chosen, the one I feel, much more than that of blood.” Here then, is an opening up to the other, with a belonging that brings like-minded beings together. We become part of a family, a history, a country. In the midst of diverse communities, there is still that belonging, that unity. Different or distant, the other is still the same as us. This ‘difference’ makes life what it is. We begin to know, accept, acknowledge and appreciate the difference through knowing each other.

France as a nation has its motto: *liberty, equality, fraternity*. But fraternity is different from the rest. Fraternity cannot be imposed by law. It is built by all of us. But, why fraternity? In this pandemic period, paradoxically, we need to build human fraternity as particular cultures are closing in. According to Véronique Albanel, a philosophy professor, fraternity is an intentional family build on solidarity, that is, “to live as a ‘family’ by welcoming others while respecting their person and their differences” (Henning, 2020). It is hospitality experienced on an equal footing. A community that engages in organizing and mobilizing as a family. Christian faith has to push us from Christian community to “community of the other”, holds Albanel. He says, a successful fraternity leads to others with solidarity, leaving extreme positions. It opens us to the larger unknown community, becoming truly the universal community (Catholic). This decisive and deliberately chosen enlarged community is at the heart of Christ intention – that all be one – not imaginary or ideal. It becomes a true and concrete human encounter. The encounter between Francis of Assisi and the Sultan at Damietta in 1219, or that between Pope Francis and the Grand Imam of Al-Azhar, Ahmed El-Tayebin, in February 2019 in Abu Dhabi, signing the document on “human fraternity”, are true examples. A movement towards a universal community. Similarly, the spirituality of Charles de Foucauld lived a life of fraternity with

the Muslim brethren, uniting all in one universal “everyone’s brother”, Jesus (Henning, 2020).⁵

“The word became brother” (flesh), (Henning, 2020)⁶ – Jesus, “the eldest of many brothers” (Rom 8: 29), whom all Christians are to follow, till the total fraternity is established, including all enemies within the family and outside. And the basis of such fraternal community is real contact. One cannot be a brother or sister unless another brother/sister relates that way. You need the other. Therefore, communal fraternity is an experience, lived with the neighbours, in daily life’s events. Quoting a Roman’s observation of the second century Christian community Tertullian, wrote, “Look, they say, how they love one another.” More than a community, it was “fraternity” (Greek word, *adelphotès*, fraternity being the proper name of the Church). In the words of Anne Lécu, a Dominican Sister, “To be brother and sister is to receive oneself from the same Father.” One cannot be brother or sister all by himself/herself. Fraternity engages in a relationship and recognizes the common humanity, - inclusive of all migrants, foreigners,

⁵ Paul VI speaks of Charles de Foucauld in his encyclical *Populorum Progressio* as - holding Jesus to be “everyone’s brother” ‘and not as the “universal brother” which is a bad translation. Cf. *Letter to Madame de Bondy* (7 January 1902). Saint Paul VI used these words in praising the saint’s commitment: Encyclical Letter *Populorum Progressio* (26 March 1967): AAS 59 (1967), 263, as referred in FT, *footnote* n.288. Charles de Foucauld, lived in Algeria, in the midst of the Tuareg Peoples, a nomadic Berber tribe. He went towards the different other, to the point of living “to work to establish the Fraternity on earth,” he declared in 1904, founding a “zaouïa”, an Islamic name for a sort of monastery or community of prayer and hospitality.

⁶ “The Word became Brother,” wrote Christian de Chergé, one of the seven Trappist monks of Tibhirine who were martyred in 1996, and beatified in 2018 among the eighteen Martyrs of Algeria. He said, “Brother of Abel and also of Cain, brother of Isaac and Ishmael at the same time, brother of Joseph and of the eleven others who sold him, brother of the plain and brother of the mountain, brother of Peter, of Judas and of both of them in me.”

neighbours and prisoners - of the same flesh. To sum it all, the only way to find the unseen God, is to recognize Him in all brothers and sisters.

“You are all brothers and sisters” (Mt 23.8). The call to universal fraternity requires openness to human beings who find their fulfilment in the sincere gift of self to others, with a love that calls for a greater ability to accept others and to reach out to the margins. A love capable of transcending borders for a greater good, is the basis of social friendship. This friendship for greater good, promotes values that advance integral human development. For, every person is valuable and “every human being has the right to live with dignity” (FT 107). This is achieved by: thinking and acting as a community; combatting the structural causes of poverty and inequality; the state being actively present and invest in assistance to the vulnerable; insuring that no one is excluded; establishing a lasting peace based on a global ethic of solidarity and service.

Vision of an Open Heart, Open to the World

Envisaging and engendering an open world (Ch. 3, FT 87-127), we are asked to move beyond ourselves engrained with the unique value of love - a love that is ever more open within open societies that integrate everyone (FT 88-98). We all suffer from the inadequate understandings of universal love (FT 99-100). Francis exhorts all to go “‘outside’ the self”, to find “a fuller existence in another” (FT 88), through the spiritual dynamism of charity leading toward “universal fulfilment” (FT 95), without selfishness (FT 92-93). It calls us to go beyond a world of “associates” with a universal love that promotes persons and lead towards liberty, equality and fraternity, while also promoting the moral good and the value of solidarity (FT 101-117). Re-envisaging the social role of property that ultimately belongs to the Creator-Giver and which needs to be shared, the rights of all peoples especially the poor and abandoned, and the rights without borders (FT 121-127) must be upheld.

A fraternal society with ethics and right to live with dignity, will promote dialogue and defeat the “virus” of “radical individualism” (FR 105). Every family needs to be protected with respect for its “primary and vital mission of education” (FT 114) with benevolence and solidarity (FT 112). All will have to fight against poverty and inequality (FT 115). Our God is universal love, and we are called to universal fraternity to share this love with an open heart, in an open world, without walls and divisions through social friendship, seeking what is morally good, and socially ethical. It is a call to solidarity, encounter and gratuitousness.

Only a *heart open to the whole world* (Ch. 4, FT 128-153)⁷, going beyond borders and their limits can bring healing in the world (FT 129-132). Through a fruitful exchange of reciprocal gifts of self and resources, a gratuitousness open to others, can there be solidarity and brotherhood (FT 137-141). This universal horizon of solidarity has to start with local region at the grass root level with a local flavour, thus connecting what is local with the universal (FT 142-153). Only a heart that opens to the whole world, works in favour of universal fraternity. It does so by: welcoming, protecting, promoting and integrating migrants, whose lives are “at stake” (FT 37), and the marginalized; becoming aware that either we *all* are saved or no one; executing a global juridical, political, and economic order that favours the development of all peoples in solidarity. To do so, *gratuitously*, we need to welcome strangers, without expecting tangible benefit; doing charity simply because they are good in themselves; serving without personal gain. For, “The true worth of the different countries of our world is measured by their ability to think as part of the larger human family. God always gives freely” (FT 139-141). All have rights to live with dignity in one’s own country. But those “fleeing grave humanitarian crises” must be given protection of citizens’ rights and assistance (FT 38-40) by

⁷ Part of the first chapter (FT 37-41) and the entire fourth chapter of FT (128-153) deal with the issues on migrants.

granting visas; opening humanitarian corridors; assuring lodging, security and essential services; offering opportunities for employment; helping in family reunification; protecting minors; guaranteeing religious freedom and promoting social inclusion by avoiding the use of the term “minorities” (FT 129-131). Any healthy culture of solidarity opens the minds and hearts to understand those who are different because differences represent an opportunity for growth (FT 133-135); in such universal fraternal communion, each human group discovers its own beauty; that this ‘limited human beings’ are limitless. As in a polyhedron – an image favorite to Francis – the whole is more than its parts, but each one of them is valued and respected (FT 145-146). It is possible to open to our neighbours within a family of nations. There is a need, therefore, for global governance, with long-term planning (FT 132) based on the principle of gratuitousness.

Social Friendship and Universal Fraternity with Dignity

The concept “social friendship” in the subtitle of FT along with fraternity, has been with Francis from 2000, then Cardinal Jorge Mario Bergoglio, Archbishop of Buenos Aires (Le Normand, 2020). He writes, “social friendship within a society makes true universal openness possible” and that a “love capable of transcending borders is the basis” (FT 99) of a genuine ‘social friendship’. This kind of friendship allowed the Good Samaritan of the parable (Lk 10: 25-37) “to interrupt his journey, change his plans, and unexpectedly come to the aid of an injured person who needed his help” (FT 101).

Social dialogue and friendship in society are paramount for a new culture, built together based on consensus and truth (FT 198-214]. Propagating a new culture of encounter, becomes a habitual joyous culture, a new-normal of acknowledging others by recovering act of kindness through concrete charity, understanding and acceptance of the other, because “no one is useless and no one is expendable” (FT 215). Dialogue and encounter allows one to respect the point of view of others. Relativism is not a solution, because without universal

principles and moral norms, laws become merely “arbitrary impositions” (FT 206; *Laudato Si*, 123). In this regard media has a special role: without exploiting human weaknesses it must be directed toward generous encounter with the least, promoting proximity and the sense of human family (FT 205). The miracle of “kindness”, has to be recovered because it is that which “frees us from the cruelty and creates a healthy coexistence and opens paths in places where exasperation burns bridges (FT 222-224).

In order to achieve “social friendship and universal fraternity”, it is necessary to “call for an acknowledgement of the worth of every human person” (FT 106). Unless this basic right to live with dignity is upheld, “there will be no future either for fraternity or for the survival of humanity” (FT 107). All those who consider the migrants and other disadvantaged people being “less human” are to be denounced. Francis writes: “This illusion, unmindful of the great fraternal values, leads to “a sort of cynicism. For that is the temptation we face if we go down the road of disenchantment and disappointment (...) Rather, it is closeness; it is the culture of encounter. Isolation, no; closeness, yes. Culture clash, no; culture of encounter, yes” (FT 30). The inalienable dignity of all people, that comes from God, is the source of fraternity; and therefore, the death penalty is “inadmissible” (FT 263) and a “just war” (Augustine, *Epistola* 229; FT, *footnote*, 242) ⁸ can never exist (FT 258).

In the Way of the Good Samaritan

Pope Francis holds that the global culture is sick with many social ills, which have been complicated by the Covid-19 pandemic. In order to overcome such ‘sickness’ we need today’s Good Samaritans, with a sense of solidarity, who gift their life, time,

⁸ Saint Augustine, who coined the phrase “just war” that no longer can be upheld, said that “it is a higher glory still to stay war itself with a word, than to slay men with the sword, and to procure or maintain peace by peace, not by war” (*Epistola* 229, 2: PL 33, 1020), as cited in FT, *footnote*, n.242.

money, energy, concerns and compassion to the neighbours on the peripheries, who are deprived and are different from us, by the very structures that the Global society has created. The poor and disabled are side-lined. We as brothers and sisters, need to share our goods with each other, because they belong to all. This has to be done with local flavour guided by universal worldview (think globally act locally!). All these are possible only through a culture of encounter that involves listening and reimagining the dividing structures. We cannot go back to the past ways of the world, instead, the ‘new normal’ is a chance to build a new society based on loving our neighbour with a vision laid down by Pope Francis in FT. The pandemics of inequality, xenophobia, individualism, ‘my-family-alone attitude’, self-seeking for comfortable living, hoarding of wealth for oneself, etc. exist today. These maladies inconvenience the poor and marginalised who are struggling through varied difficulties in life. It turns into bigger problems, expanding to a global scale, when the wealthy exploit the poor and economic inequality grows. While pockets of progress happen, the poor, the elderly and the disabled are left behind, and the gap is widened.

The solution to all these problems comes from the biblical parable of the Good Samaritan. The context of the parable is, *a stranger on the road* (Ch. 2, FT 56-86), abandoned on the wayside - a story constantly retold today of rape victims or victims of communal violence (FT 63-71). The various characters of the story (FT 72-76) are all part of each of us. Part of all the characters, namely, the assailants, the passers-by (Levite, Pharisee), the wounded and abandoned victim are in most of us. In the face of such reality, we question: who is my neighbour? Francis says, “Jesus asks us not to decide who is close enough to be our neighbour, but rather that we ourselves become neighbours to all” (FT 80). FT summons us to be actively involved in rehabilitating our wounded societies. The story of the Good Samaritan is being repeated today: determinism or fatalism are recourse to, in order to justify our own indifference. The elite ‘throwaway’ society tends to ignore others, especially the

weak. Often the governance and state authorities allow and encourage social exclusion. Today, we are witnessing ‘social distance’ and political apathy. True love in social friendship does not care if one in need comes from one place or another. For, love shatters the chains that keep us isolated and separate; it builds bridges. In the face of suffering, the only course is to imitate the Good Samaritan. What is learnt here is a decision to start anew as a Good Samaritan, meet the needs of the neighbours without borders (FT 77-83) and hear and respond positively to the pleas of the strangers (FT 84-86), who are different from us. Discovering a discarded and injured stranger, one can have two attitudes: ignore or help. An inclusive or exclusive attitude will define the person we are, and which political, social or religious group we belong to. In an unhealthy and “illiterate” society that cares less for the frail and vulnerable (FT 64-65), we need to become neighbours to others (FT 81), and be co-responsible in creating a society without prejudices, self-interests, and cultural barriers (FT 77). Love builds bridges and “we were made for love” (FT 88) according to “a universal dimension” (FT 83), recognizing Christ in the face of every excluded person (FT 85).

It is not just that the Samaritan was an outsider showing concern for a stranger, a neighbour different from him, or that the priest and the Levite, the religious leaders ignored him, following protocols. The Samaritan gives his time, prioritizing in helping the affected stranger. He enters into an encounter. The first step in building a healthier society starts with such encounter with our neighbours, people who are different and are struggling. This leads one to be aware of the larger social issues that cause others to suffer: the political and social structure that need to change and recognize the universal destination of goods, for as the early Church held, the earthly resources are not for us to hoard, but to be shared. It is a fact, while some nations hoard up tons and tons of food, others go through famines. The gap between the haves and have-nots widen.

When such big divide happens, the deprived ones naturally pursue better opportunities and migrate to other places. While doing so, the global society which one falls prey to, does harm to local cultures. The migrants lose their unique cultures. Therefore, care must be taken to provide good opportunities in the places that people are born. If that does not happen, migrants have to be welcomed with respect and friendships and not treating them as nuisance and act violently against them (FT 132-133). We need to act locally with a universal worldview. There has to be a movement towards peace and universal brotherhood. This is what Francis calls a culture based on encounter, involving listening, accepting, and ‘reimagining the structures’ that cause people to suffer. This means, giving strangers time like the Good Samaritan on an international level. It means listening to poor nations, involving them in decision-making, to find what is best for all people. As brothers and sisters we need to come out better by ridding ourselves of our individualistic attitudes and build a culture of collaboration, dialogue and encounter.

Jesus summarises the greatest commandment in the Bible: “You shall love the Lord, your God, with all your heart, with all your being, with all your strength, and with all your mind, and your neighbour as yourself “(Lk 10:40). All of religion and humanity is about having a loving heart for God and for creation, including men and women, filled with compassion and care. This is so, because Jesus is Christ, who is God-man, in whom divinity and humanity meet. Therefore, the love of God, with logical consistency and spiritual integrity, necessarily draws us to a love for all our brothers and sisters – the whole human race (Barron, 2020).

Better Kind of Politics at the Service of the Common Good

The world needs *a better kind of politics* (Ch. 5, FT 154-197) with positive and pro-active forms of populism and liberalism, thus distinguishing ‘popular’ from what is ‘populist’ (FT 155-162). To create an open world with an open heart, a better kind of politics for the common and universal good is essential, politics that is

“popular”, practising social charity out of “political love by integrating the economy with the social and cultural fabric into a consistent and life-giving human project” (Catholic Telegraph, 2020). Politics is meant to be at the service of the common good (FT 180) and makes it possible for people discuss and dialogue (FT 160) in a democratic way, and not fomenting selfishness in order to increase its own popularity (FT 159). It protects work, an “essential dimension of social life”, and enables everyone to develop their own abilities (FT 162), ultimately to have a dignified life.

Certainly, there are benefits and limits of modern days’ liberal approaches (FT 163-169). The international powers, including the UNO, must work through social and political charity (FT 170-185), and promote the force of law rather than the law of force, by favouring multilateral accords that better protect even the weakest states. The United Nations must give substance to the concept of a “family of nations” working for the common good and the protection of human rights (FT 173-175).

We need politics impregnated with political love (FT 177-182). It is a universally effective love with a local flavour (FT183-185). The exercise of political love has to be manifested through selfless sacrifices born of love, a love that integrates and unites (FT 186-192), with solidarity and subsidiarity (FT 187). According to Francis, politics has to guarantee fundamental human rights, and resolve social exclusion; sale of organs, weapons and drugs; sexual exploitation and human trafficking; slave labour; terrorism and organized crime which are to be eliminated. For him, hunger, is “criminal”, because food is “an inalienable right” (FT 188-189). We have to measure its success with fruitfulness over results (FT193-197). Dialogue built on social friendship, is the basis for a better politics that seeks the truth. Dialogue that leads to a culture of encounter with respect, in turn becomes a passionate way of life.

“Charity, according to the teaching of Jesus, is the synthesis of the entire Law” (cf. Mt 22:36-40). Manipulation of laws for political gain, destroys politics itself. We need a better kind of politics, one that: truly promotes the common good; does not seek electoral gains; serves as a channel for personal/fraternal growth; promotes an economy that favours productive diversity and business creativity; is far-sighted and capable of a new, integral and interdisciplinary dialogue. Therefore, FT calls for a social and political order whose soul is social charity: making it advance towards a civilization of love; recognizing *all* human beings as brothers and sisters. Charity through socio-political activities needs the light of truth, the light of reason and the light of faith. Social charity makes us love the common good; it makes us effectively seek the good of all people, in the social dimension that unites them. In socio-political activity, every person is sacred and deserves our affection and our respect, and if at least one person is helped to have a better life, that “already justifies the offering of my life” (FT 195).

Francis, therefore, writes a ‘political encyclical’⁹ based on theological and spiritual foundations, affirms his direct positions (FT 120)¹⁰ asserting what he says, and observes reactions for further dialogue and debate having political implications, just as the Gospel has. Though FT is not a dogmatic discourse, Francis shifts his points of view with risks, from secular to religious principles. For example, the concrete application on cancelling the debt of poor countries or no to *just war*¹¹, is not so simple, and can be debatable. But he expresses his point of view in fraternity. Similarly, his move

⁹ Encyclicals are quite regularly political, like the one written by Leo XIII (*Au milieu des sollicitudes*, on the Church and State in France in 1892), Pius XI on communism and Nazism, or John Paul II.

¹⁰ For example, Francis confuses and compromises when he assures that the natural right to private property will be secondary to the principal of the universal destination of created goods (FT 120).

¹¹ Francis’ intervention in Mali in 2013, for example, helped to protect the population.

towards decentralization in the Church and the culture of dialogue, can shake up the Church, yet he takes the risk of making people react (Noé, 2020).

Christian Socio-Political Task: Not to Be Naïve

Pope Francis has criticised “neo-liberal” system, “populism” and the claim for “individualistic-rights” (FT 111); he makes a harsh observation of excesses globalization, financial systems, and attitudes towards migrants whose fundamental rights are violated. But he does not provide any lines of action for putting an end to them. FT may seem to be too political for a spiritual leader, but it is his fight against the great evils that are plaguing today’s world. In a less diplomatic style, with a “left-wing” label attached to him, Francis tries to renew the language of the Church, following a radical Gospel path.

As head of state, as a great spiritual and political leader, he is charting a “common course” for humanity, on concrete situations drawn from the many national episcopal conferences that report on tragic events, violent conflicts and the civil wars in the world. He is, therefore, at the service of conflict resolution. With frankness, he diagnoses and confronts the political aberrations, going out of the confine of spiritual sphere. He prides where it hurts, by “attacking the various logics that exclude the poorest” (de Neuville, 2020)¹² and exposes the economic, societal and cultural systems that produce the “culture of waste”- a “throwaway culture” (FT 188).

Radical social Catholicism must take up the task at this perilous moment of politics of the powerful. Catholic world is underperforming in public life, though its social doctrine, poorly known and insufficiently appreciated by the faithful, is admired

¹² Marcel Rémon SJ, an expert on Catholic social teaching, a professor of geopolitics and director of the Center for Social Research and Action (CERAS), makes the statement.

outside. Persons inspired by Christian thinking kept a balance between personal responsibility and a concern for community, between individual rights and the common good. Today, we hear from Church leaders, the cry of cultural warfare, of gloom and danger, than the equilibrium of rights and duties, responsibility, hope and possibilities. The Church's socio-political teachings with radical moderation is missing today. In this context, FT offers a sharp critique of the *status quo* and at the same time sees human beings capable of transcendence in the face of growing inequality. As *Rerum novarum* insists on the dignity of work and the right of workers to organize collectively to maintain their family life and its values, FT empathizes with those outside the families with social friendship, to form a fraternity (FT 162; Francis, 2015, 2014).

It has to bring to the world “the joy of the Gospel,” with charity and justice by speaking fearlessly and consistently against the social and moral failures. Church's public witness is what Francis offers with decisive steps, towards democracy, religious freedom, and human rights. To be a “counter-cultural” force, one has to be critical of the *status quo*, with a monolithic political views based on the Gospel. But, Francis's most enthusiastic detractors speak about “intrinsic evils,” towards which he is leading the Church, because he speaks boldly, on migrants, racism, labour rights, climate change, social justice, war, economics and death penalty.

If we do not disassociate from right-wing politics, there will not be any progressive Catholicism (Dionne, 2020)¹³; the young will dismiss the institutions of faith and religious people; the more we are with secularism and the doctrine of moral relativism, the

¹³ The decline of progressive Catholicism reflects a reorientation of the hierarchy during the John Paul II and Benedict years, and a transformation of the Church's social base. A 2015 Pew Research report found that 13% of former Americans Catholics, now identify with other religious traditions. Only half of millennials (57%) raised Catholic have remained in the Church. Most of the Catholic are older and, more conservative.

traditional moral order will die in misery. We can never question the sincerity of another's faith, which is the mysterious gift of grace. Certainly, there are conflicting attitudes toward Francis's project. Creating a culture of life, rooted in solidarity, dialogue and conversion will go a long way to cease the vicious cycle the culture wars have let loose. Pope Francis says, "If the Church is alive, it must always surprise." (Francis, 2014; see also Wenders, 2018; FT footnote, 278)¹⁴

Paths of Renewed Encounter and Forgiveness

The *paths of renewed encounter* have to start anew from the truth, which is the art and architecture of peace, because without righteousness or justice there is no peace (FT 225-235). The process of encounter begins with the least in the society, through the value and meaning of forgiveness (FT 233-245). The renewed community will have to confront the inevitable conflict, the legitimate conflict through forgiveness that brings about reunion of brothers and sisters under one universal bond of brotherhood (FT 237-243). Francis stresses that fraternity and friendship in society are the means to build a better, fairer and more peaceful world. For this, one has to face and acknowledge the past mis-encounters, and work on re-encounter (FT Ch. 7; cf. Catholic Telegraph, 2020), in order to heal the past wounds through forgiveness. This is the best way to move on with memory, which is, forgiving but not forgetting (FT 244-254). One has to dare, confront the inevitable conflict, and acknowledge the historical truth in order to win justice which is

¹⁴ Francis told this in St Peter's Square on Pentecost Sunday 2014. "If the Church is alive, it must always surprise [...] A Church that doesn't have the capacity to surprise is a weak, sickened and dying Church." FT n. 281 quotes, "God does not see with his eyes, God sees with his heart. And God's love is the same for everyone, regardless of religion. Even if they are atheists, his love is the same. When the last day comes, and there is sufficient light to see things as they really are, we are going to find ourselves quite surprised". It is taken from the film *Pope Francis: A Man of His Word*, by Wim Wenders (2018).

indispensable for establishing peace without violence, saying no to war and a “globalised indifference”(FT 30). Total elimination of nuclear arms is “a moral and humanitarian imperative” (FT 262; cf. Francis, 2017: 394-396). No more injustices (just wars), instead use the fund for eliminating hunger in the world (FT 255-262). So too, the death penalty is inadmissible, and it is to be abolished (FT 263-270) precisely because of the respect for “the sacredness of life” (FT 283), which cannot be readily sacrificed, such as the unborn, the poor, the disabled and the elderly (FT 184).

The processes of renewed encounter are necessary on the path toward peace and they are: true reconciliation; common projects without denying individuality; recognizing, protecting and restoring the dignity of all; with option for the poor, the dispossessed and the marginalized; practising forgiveness. Jesus, who was against violence or intolerance, tells us to forgive “seventy times seven” (Mt 18:22). True forgiveness and reconciliation are achieved in conflict and are resolved through dialogue, by abstaining from enmities and mutual hatred. It facilitates an honest discussion of differences, founded on a desire for justice, without forgetting or impunity, so that the individuals or communities may not fall into the vicious circle of vengeance. Pope Francis, therefore says, “I ask God to prepare our hearts to encounter our brothers and sisters, so that we may overcome our differences rooted in political thinking, language, culture and religion” (FT 254, footnote 236; see also Francis, May 2014).

Peace and Justice through Inter-Faith Fraternal Dialogue

Peace-building is an “art” that “involves us all” with “a never-ending task” (FT 232). It is not absence of war but a “tireless commitment” for responsible leaders, “to recognize, protect and concretely restore the dignity” of brothers and sisters (FT 233). Peace, connected to truth, justice and mercy, is ‘proactively’ aims at forming a society based on service to others in the pursuit of reconciliation and mutual development (FT 227-229), where

everyone must feel “at home”. The peace process places the human person, his or her dignity and the common good at the centre of all activity (FT 230-232). Forgiveness without forgetting, is a precondition for peace. By not forgetting, one chooses “not to yield to the same destructive force that caused them so much suffering” (FT 251). Confronting injustice, one must defend his rights in order to safeguard his God-given dignity (241- 242). Forgiveness does not mean impunity, but rather, justice and remembrance, renouncing the destructive power of evil. Horrors of the past memory keep the flame of collective conscience alive so that we do not become anaesthetized, and remember the good, and those who have chosen forgiveness and fraternity (FT 246-252). It “enables us to pursue justice without falling into a spiral of revenge or the injustice of forgetting” (FT 252). A journey of peace among religions has to begin with God’s way of seeing things, for God sees with his heart. Fundamental religious convictions abhor violence. Sincere and humble worship of God, through diverse religious rituals and traditions, bears fruit in respect for life, dignity and freedom. Therefore, religious leaders are called to be true “people of dialogue” and “authentic mediators” (FT 284) in order to cooperate in building peace.

All *religions of the world* (Ch. 8, FT 271-287) will have to be at the service of enhancing fraternity in our world - the ultimate foundation of universal brotherhood and unity. As God’s creatures, with different religious affiliations, we are called to the *service of fraternity* (Ch. 8) by establishing social friendship. With an openness to the Father of all, we recognize our universal brotherhood and sisterhood. Jesus Christ and his message inspire all Christian actions and commitments towards fraternity, starting with the recognition that we are all brothers and sisters.

Violence has no basis in religious convictions, and terrorism is due to erroneous interpretations of religious texts, as well as “policies linked to hunger, poverty, injustice, oppression” (Ft 283). It is an

international crime against security and world peace, and it must be condemned (FT 282-283). With memory of injustice and violence inflicted upon different faith communities, the Christian identity must be purged of all hateful prejudices and superiority (FT 277-284), and establish social friendship with the members of other religions, in order to live as brothers and sisters under the same Creator, in an inter-faith and ecumenical spirit (FT 285-287). Religions are called to be at the service of fraternity in the world. Only with the awareness that we are all children of single Creator, can we live in peace within the society. The different religions do contribute to building fraternity. It is, therefore, necessary to guarantee religious freedom - a fundamental human right for all believers (FT 279). Seeking God helps us recognize one another as travelling companions. Instead, the denial of religious freedom and freedom of conscience leaves humanity impoverished and divided. In this context, the Catholic Church as a home, opens her doors, because She is a mother who builds, breaks down walls and sows seeds of reconciliation. She does not “restrict her mission to the private sphere” (FT 276), staying at the margin, renouncing the political dimension of life itself. The Church has to attend to the common good and to integral human development, according to evangelical principals (FT 278).

Dialogue and Friendship in Society means: approaching, speaking, and listening in order to know and understand one another, and find the common ground. Through a culture of encounter, each person can learn something from others, that no one is useless, and no one is expendable. A pluralist society that encourages dialogue, respects the dignity of others in all circumstances and integrates differences, thus guaranteeing a genuine and lasting peace. It recognizes other people’s right to be themselves, creating an atmosphere of friendliness. Certain attitudes or actions that do not help towards a genuine dialogue are: any aggression manifested, e.g. on social networks; monologues; humiliating and discrediting others. “Authentic

social dialogue involves the ability to respect the other's point of view" (FT 203).

Conclusion

Fratelli Tutti, "You are all brothers" (Mt 23:8) and sisters. Therefore, God is our Father. So together we pray, "Our Father", hallowed be your name." (Lk 11.1-4) implying that we might make it holy for us, that God might be honored above all. Everything else in the spiritual life flows from this prioritization. "Your Kingdom come." God's kingdom refers to God's way of ordering things. Jesus' teaching and his manner of life give us a very good idea of what this kingdom would look like: peace, nonviolence, forgiveness, healing, walking the path of compassion. In fact, while the Good Samaritan is proposed as a style of responding amid these epic times, Pope Francis recalls Martin Luther King, Desmond Tutu, Mahatma Gandhi and Blessed Charles de Foucauld, as models for everyone to imbibe these qualities, and to identify with the least in order to become "the universal brother" (FT 286-287). Recalling these great leaders, Pope Francis reminds the world religious leaders to be "authentic mediators" and makes appeal that, in the name of human fraternity, dialogue be adopted as the way, common cooperation as conduct, and mutual knowledge as method and standard (FT 285; see also Francis, 2019).¹⁵

Pope Francis is only a human being, *a fratello*, and he can be wrong. Criticizing his words and actions need not make one an ideologue. What is needed, is to forgive each other as brothers and sisters. We often pray, "Forgive us our sins for we ourselves forgive everyone in debt to us." Forgiveness is central to the teaching of Jesus and to the suffering of the world where people are incapable to forgive,

¹⁵ Pope Francis quotes from the *Document on Human Fraternity for World Peace and Living Together*, which he signed on 4 February 2019 in Abu Dhabi, along with the Grand Imam of Al-Azhar, Ahmad Al-Tayyib: a milestone of interreligious dialogue.

both on the smallest, most intimate level and on the grandest, geopolitical scale. Through the last two prayers, one to the Creator and one ecumenical, Francis teaches us to plead with God as brothers and sisters, that we be given the grace to forgive and be united to love, and live in fraternity and social friendship. God invites us to co-create with Him a new world built on love, justice, equality, and together inspire change of policies, practices, and behaviour at all levels, from government to grassroots communities. We, therefore, pray “to the Creator” in an inter-faith and ecumenical spirit, so that the heart of mankind may harbour “a spirit of fraternity” and friendship: “Trinity of love, from the profound communion of your divine life, pour out upon us a torrent of fraternal love (...) discovering Christ in each human being, recognizing him crucified in the sufferings of the abandoned and forgotten of our world, and risen in each brother or sister who makes a new start” (FT, ecumenical prayer).¹⁶

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